

Spectral dependence of split ratio, loss and polarization extinction ratio in commercial polarization-maintaining fiber couplers

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Abstract: This document presents the results of broadband spectral characterization of commercial polarization-maintaining fiber couplers. The investigated couplers were four Y-couplers from Thorlabs fabricated with PANDA-type fibers with 50:50 split ratio for a slow mode at different wavelengths: 780 nm, 850 nm, 980 nm and 1550 nm. The manufacturer provides an approximate split ratio and the bandwidth of operation only for the slow mode, a single wavelength, and one port. The results of this study reveal the split ratio for both polarization modes between all ports and in both directions of light transmission in the spectral range from 450 to 1750 nm. Additionally, spectral dependence of polarization extinction ratio was measured. A comparison of the results for two couplers of the same model is also included, demonstrating good repeatability in the coupler fabrication process.
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1. Introduction

The datasheets provided by the manufacturers of the polarization-maintaining (PM) fiber couplers are usually limited and most often show the split ratio only for a single polarization mode, a single wavelength, and a specific transmission direction, as well as a very general value of polarization extinction ratio (e.g., >18 dB) for one wavelength. This restricted information can be insufficient for applications that rely on broadband operation or the use of both polarization modes.

The goal of this study was to reveal broadband spectral characteristics of commercially available polarization-maintaining Y-couplers (with one input port and two output ports as shown in Fig. 1) fabricated using PANDA-type fibers. The investigation focused on the spectral dependence of split ratio, polarization extinction ratio (PER) and transmission with insertion loss for an FC/APC connector. Four models with a nominal 50:50 split ratio for the slow polarization mode, designed for operation at central wavelengths of 780 nm, 850 nm, 980 nm, and 1550 nm, finished with FC/APC connectors were investigated, particularly PN780R5A1, PN850R5A1, PN980R5A1 (two pieces) and PNH1550R5A1 models provided by Thorlabs. The measurements were conducted over a wide spectral range from 450 nm to 1750 nm for both polarization modes in all possible transmission directions. Additionally, by comparing the results for two couplers of the same model, the consistency and repeatability of the fabrication process were estimated.

The motivation behind this study was to determine the possibility of applying commercially available PM fiber couplers as filters for pulse delivery to all-fiber optically pumped single-photon sources. The idea focuses on the bi-directional transmission of the 1x2 coupler in the following manner:

- (a) pumping laser of shorter wavelength (e.g. 805 nm) and given polarization is coupled into one of the two output ports of the coupler,
- (b) semiconductor all-fiber quantum-dot-based single-photon source (as described in [1]) is connected to the input port of the coupler,
- (c) light delivered from the pumping laser to the source excites the quantum dot (QD) and results in emission of longer-wavelength photons (e.g. 1300 nm),
- (d) the photons emitted by the quantum dot and part of the pumping laser light reflected from the semiconductor sample are coupled back into the same fiber,
- (e) the fiber coupler filters the remaining pumping laser photons, leaving only the emitted single photons from the quantum dot at the second output port.

Ideally, the split ratio at the wavelength of pulse delivery should be 0:100 for both polarization modes, ensuring that all the light is transmitted to the sample and that the light reflected from the sample or scattered is fully filtered and does not exit the source together with the photons emitted by the QD. Additionally, at the QD emission wavelength, the split ratio should be 100:0 with possibly low loss, allowing all the photons to exit the source.

Fig. 1. Picture of the coupler with the port indicators used across this document. Source: Thorlabs.

2. Experimental setup

The light source used for characterization was the supercontinuum SuperK Compact from NKT Photonics. As a spectral detector, an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) Yokogawa AQ63874 was used. Overlapping spectrum of the source and the detector was 450–1750 nm. All spectra were registered using a resolution of 2 nm and HIGH1 sensitivity on the OSA.

To couple the light in and out of the fiber, two Plan Apo 20x objectives from Mitutoyo and two NanoMAX stages from Thorlabs with precise 3-axis adjustment screws were used. To control the polarization, wire-grid polarizers (Thorlabs WP25M-UB1 operating in the range from 300 to 3200 nm) were added to the setup: before the incoupling objective and after the outcoupling objective.

To ensure the same position of the light spot at the slit of the OSA, a broadband calcium-fluoride beam splitter was added at the output of the fiber, directing part of the beam to a camera. The uneven coupling ratio of the beam splitter in the spectral range from 450 to 800 nm does not affect the transmission characteristics presented here, as the results were calculated as a difference between two signals registered with the same beam splitter in the same position.

To measure the coupling ratio and PER, the light was coupled directly into one of the ports of the couplers. To measure the transmission and coupling ratio including insertion loss, the light was coupled into a single-mode PANDA-type patchcord, the spectra for the patchcord alone were registered, and then the output connector of the patchcord was connected to one of the ports of the investigated coupler and the corresponding transmission spectrum was recorded. To connect the patchcord and the coupler port, a mating sleeve dedicated to PM fibers was used (Thorlabs ADAFCPM1).

2.1. Transmission

The transmission including insertion loss was measured as a difference between the spectra measured for the patchcord and the same patchcord connected to the coupler.

2.2. PER

The PER was calculated as a difference between transmission and extinction spectra of the same mode. To ensure the proper launch polarization, firstly the maximum extinction was found, and for the transmission the analyzer was rotated by 90°. The length of the fibers in the investigated couplers was approximately 1 m for each port. For such a short length of the PM fibers, during the PER measurement when the input and output polarizers are crossed, the residual interference between the polarization modes is observed. These interference fringes slightly shift spectrally over time due to fluctuations in temperature and fiber bending. Therefore, the PER values shown in the figures in the Results section were calculated after filtering out the fringes with a moving average smoothing filter. The example interference fringes and the filtered signal used for analysis are shown in Fig. 2. One should note that, due to this interference, the PER values might fluctuate by up to a few dB in some parts of the spectra. Nonetheless, the results presented here are in good agreement with the parameters provided by Thorlabs and confirm that for all couplers, at the wavelength of the couplers operation the PER is above the values assured by the manufacturer, as shown later in Table 1 in the Results section.

Fig. 2. Interference fringes between the polarization modes observed during the PER measurement before and after filtering with a moving average filter.

2.3. Coupling ratio

This coupling ratio was calculated as the ratio of the output power from a given output port to the sum of the powers at both output ports.

2.4. Coupling ratio including insertion and transmission loss

This coupling ratio was calculated as the ratio of the output power from a given port to the output power of the patchcord used to launch the light into the input coupler port (see section 2.1. *Transmission*).

3. Results

This section contains spectra of all the measured parameters for each investigated coupler. For all couplers, the same spectra were measured in both directions, i.e., the spectrum transmitted from the white input port to the white/red output port and from the white/red output port to the white input port. In both directions, the transmission was nearly identical, with changes of up to 0.5 dB in most of the spectrum. Larger deviations were only observed near the cutoff of transmission of any of the coupler arms (caused either by transmission loss of the fiber itself or

Fig. 3. Comparison of the spectral transmission from the white input port to both output ports and in the opposite direction for the PN780R5A1 coupler.

by the coupling ratio approaching 100:0) for longer wavelengths and in the spectral range where the fibers become few-mode on the shorter wavelength side. Example results for the PN780R5A1 coupler are shown in Fig. 3. Similar results were obtained for all the other couplers.

Figures 4–7 contain the spectral dependence of insertion and transmission loss, coupling ratio, coupling ratio calculated including the loss, and PER for PN780R5A1, PN850R5A1, PN980R5A1, and PNH1550R5A1 couplers, respectively. Additionally, in Table 1 a comparison of the data provided by the manufacturer with the measured data is shown at the wavelength of the coupler design from the white input port to both output ports for the slow axis launch. The results are consistent with the reference values, and the small deviations are within the measurement error.

The PER values shown in the spectra drop sharply around the wavelengths where the transmission of the particular channel decreases. This is caused by a strongly uneven coupling ratio between the polarization modes. It is especially evident when the coupling ratio approaches 0:100. In such a case, the PER can also drop below 0 dB. This means that due to the much higher power of the cross-polarized mode being transmitted, more of this mode is transmitted than the mode under measurement.

Fig. 4. Spectral dependence of the insertion and transmission loss, coupling ratio, coupling ratio calculated including the insertion and transmission loss, and PER for the PN780R5A1 coupler.

The discrepancies observed for the measured PER values given in Table 1 and in Figs. 4–7 are due to the differences in the measurement procedures. During the broadband measurement, the maximum extinction was found as an average for the whole measured spectrum. For the values given in Table 1 the measurement was focused around the design wavelength. Therefore, the values given in the table are higher.

Fig. 5. Spectral dependence of the insertion and transmission loss, coupling ratio, coupling ratio calculated including the insertion and transmission loss, and PER for the PN850R5A1 coupler.

Fig. 6. Spectral dependence of the insertion and transmission loss, coupling ratio, coupling ratio calculated including the insertion and transmission loss, and PER for the PN980R5A1 coupler.

Fig. 7. Spectral dependence of the insertion and transmission loss, coupling ratio, coupling ratio calculated including the insertion and transmission loss, and PER for the PNH1550R5A1 coupler.

Table 1. Comparison of data provided by the manufacturer of the couplers with measured values.

coupler model		PN780R5A1		PN850R5A1		PN980R5A1		PNH1550R5A1	
design wavelength		780 nm		850 nm		980 nm		1550 nm	
output port		white	red	white	red	white	red	white	red
insertion loss [dB]	reference	-3.64	-3.56	-3.17	-3.26	-3.33	-3.18	-3.11	-3.20
	measured	-3.82	-3.75	-3.86	-3.73	-4.02	-3.67	-3.03	-2.78
coupling ratio	reference	49.6	50.4	50.5	49.5	49.1	50.9	50.5	49.5
	measured	49.6	50.4	50.7	49.2	48.0	52.0	48.5	51.5
PER [dB]	reference	30.0	25.4	22.2	21.1	31.7	27.8	26.8	30.3
	measured	31.0	26.6	22.1	23.5	29.8	26.8	28.6	30.5

Figure 8 contains the comparison of the transmission spectra for two pieces of the same coupler model (PN980R5A1). Only minor discrepancies are noticeable from piece to piece in the entire considered spectral range, indicating good repeatability of the coupler fabrication process. The largest deviations are observed in the spectral range, where the fibers become few-mode and close to the transmission cut-off above 1500 nm.

Fig. 8. Spectral dependence of the transmission for two pieces of the same coupler model PN980R5A1.

Additionally, the back reflection from the red output port to the white output port and in the reverse direction was measured, and for the whole spectral range considered in this study, it was below -60 dB for all the couplers, except PN780R5A1, for which it was approximately -52 dB.

4. Discussion

Based on the split ratio graphs in Figs. 4–7, it can be concluded that the couplers work as 50:50 couplers for more than one wavelength for different polarization modes. For instance, the PN980R5A1 coupler (Fig. 6) designed for a slow mode and 980 nm wavelength has nearly identical split ratio and loss for the same polarization mode at 1230 nm and for the orthogonally polarized mode at 885 nm and 1070 nm. Additionally, it divides power equally at 1450 nm, however, due to insertion and transmission loss at this wavelength the power transmitted to each output port is approximately 17% of the input power.

By analyzing the losses and split ratios at different wavelengths, it can be concluded that these couplers can be used as pulse delivery filters to single-photon sources for a few wavelengths. For example, using the PN850R5A1 coupler, the laser light at a wavelength of 600 nm and matching the slow polarization mode can be delivered to the QD through the white output port. The light from the QD sample connected to the white input port emitted at the wavelength of approximately 970 nm will then be transmitted to the red output port independently of its polarization. At the same time, the laser light reflected from the sample back to the fiber will be cut out completely in the red output thanks to the losses being approximately 20 dB for both polarization modes at the wavelength of the laser operation. Further filtering can be done with a single fiber Bragg grating filter to achieve the required 60 dB of suppression.

Such wavelength combination (600 nm excitation and 970 nm emission) is realistic and can be used for instance with InAs-based QDs. Unfortunately, at the 970 nm wavelength the red port has insertion losses of approximately 0.8 dB for the slow polarization (matching the laser) and 2.7 dB for the orthogonal polarization. By adjusting the cavity properties (for example adding slight ellipticity in the proper direction), the light emitted by the QD might be mostly matching the laser polarization, and therefore, match the slow polarization of the the coupler with lower losses. Even lower losses can be achieved by outcoupling the photons from the red output to the next fiber with use of an ultra-low-loss splice instead of an FC/APC connector for at least a few excitation-emission wavelength combinations.

5. Conclusions

The goal of this study was to provide spectral characteristics of commercially available PM fiber couplers designed for different wavelengths. The results are in good agreement with the data provided by the couplers manufacturer for a single wavelength. By comparing the results for two couplers of the same model, it can be concluded that the coupler fabrication process is well-repeatable.

The detailed characterization conducted within this study was a necessary step in preparation for the application of the PM fibers in development of PM-fiber-coupled single-photon sources. Based on the obtained results it can be concluded that the commercially available couplers can be used as pulse delivery filters to the semiconductor-QD-based all-fiber single-photon sources.

Data availability Raw data for all the results shown in this document are available from the author upon request.

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